

Expert evaluation

This evaluation aims to compare the outputs of an LLM model and a MILP Solver in the context of service placement across edge nodes driven by user intents.

The experiments were conducted on four datasets, each containing a set of services to be placed along with their requirements, a set of edge nodes with their capabilities, and a set of user intents.

There are also values for end-to-end latency between the user and each of the available nodes.

To be placed, there are a set of requirements:

1. Unique Service Placement

Each service must be placed on exactly one node (server/machine).

2. Service-Intention Link

If a service belonging to an intention is placed on a node, then that intention uses that node.

Example: If intention "i2" requires services s2 and s3, and s2 is placed on node n1, then intention i2 uses node n1.

3. Node Capacity

The sum of resources used by all services on a node must not exceed that node's capacity.

Resources involved: CPU, MEM (memory), DISK, BW (bandwidth)

Example: If n1 has 8 CPU available, we cannot place services that require a total of 10 CPU on it.

4. Quality of Service (QoS) for Each Intention

a) Maximum Latency

The total latency for an intention must stay below the requested limit.

Example: If intention i1 requires a max latency of 60ms, the sum of latencies from all nodes used must be ≤ 60 ms.

b) Minimum Bandwidth

The total bandwidth provided must be at least equal to what is requested.

Example: If intention i3 requests 90 bandwidth, the services must provide at minimum 90.

5. Extra Resources (optional)

Some intentions may request resources in addition to those of the services.

These additional resources are taken into account once per intention.

For each dataset, experts are asked to evaluate the placement corresponding to each user intent and select the better option. This includes cases where the two models produce different outputs, as well as cases where only one model generates a result.

For instance, since both models produced identical outputs for Dataset 1, no expert evaluation is required for that dataset.

* **Indique une question obligatoire**

Dataset 2 Evaluation

The dataset dataset_2.json can be accessed through the following [link](#).

Only the **LLM-based model** produced results.

LLM-based model results:

- Intent i1 → s1 → Node g1
- Intent i2 → s2 → Node n2 / s3 → Node n3
- Intent i3 → s4 → Node n2 / s5 → Node n3
- Intent i4 → s5, s6 → Node n3
- Intent i5 → s1, s2, s3, s4 → Node n3
- Intent i6 → No results produced

1. Question 1:

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For each intent i , do you consider the placement compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Yes	No
Intent i1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Dataset 3 Evaluation

The dataset [dataset_3.json](#) can be accessed through the following [link](#).

Both models produced the same results for intent *i1*.

Please investigate the remaining differences for intents *i2* to *i5*.

Model outputs:

LLM-based model results:

- Intent i2 → Node n2
- Intent i3 → Node n1
- Intent i4 → Node n3
- Intent i5 → Node n3
- Intent i6 → No results produced

MILP Solver results:

Intent i1 → s1 → Node g1

Intent i2 → s2 → Node n3 / s3 → Node n3

Intent i3 → s4 → Node n2 / s5 → Node n2

Intent i4 → s5 → Node n2 / s6 → Node n2

Intent i5 → s1 → Node g1 / s2 → Node n3 / s3 → Node n3 / s4 → Node n2

Intent i6 → s1 → Node g1 / s2 → Node n3 / s3 → Node n3 / s4 → Node n2 / s5 → Node n2 / s6 → Node n2

2. Question 2:

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For intents *i2* to *i5*, which placement do you consider better?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	LLM-based	MILP Solver	Both	None
Intent i2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. **Question 3:**

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For intent ***i6***, do you consider the placement produced by the **MILP solver** compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

Une seule réponse possible.

Yes

No

Dataset 4 Evaluation

The dataset [dataset_4.json](#) can be accessed through the following [link](#).
Both models produced the same results for most intents.

Please investigate the remaining differences for intents ***i8*** and ***i31***.

4. **Here are the details of intents *i8* and *i31*:**

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```
{"id": "i8", "description": "Detect wear or damage on conveyor belt.", "services":
```

```
["s5"], "QoS": {"latency": 120, "bandwidth": 60}, "weight": 7},
```

```
{"id": "i31", "description": "Detect wear or damage on gearbox teeth.", "services":
```

```
["s5"], "QoS": {"latency": 120, "bandwidth": 60}, "weight": 7}
```

Model outputs:

LLM-based model:

- Intent *i8*: s5 → Node n12

- Intent *i31*: s5 → Node n12

MILP Solver:

No results provided

Question 5:

For intents *i8* and *i31*, do you consider the placement compliant with the service requirements and node capabilities?

Une seule réponse possible par ligne.

	Yes	No
Intent i8	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Intent i31	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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